

Resources as a Driver of Innovation of Insurance companies in Kenya

By

Dr. Beatrice Elesani Ombaka, PhD
Senior Lecturer, Karatina University, Kenya
Corresponding email: bombaka@karu.ac.ke

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of organizational resources on innovation of insurance companies in Kenya. This study proposes that resources owned by a firm if deployed effectively can lead to innovativeness. In spite of a growing body of literature on Innovation, explaining why firms in the same industry differ in their innovation remains a fundamental question amongst researchers. Researchers have attributed differences in innovation to resources owned by a firm. This study contributes to existing knowledge by establishing the effect of resources on the firm's propensity to innovate. The study was anchored on the resource-based theory and dynamic capabilities theory. The main objective of the study was to establish the effect of resources on innovation of insurance Companies in Kenya. The study employed a cross-sectional survey design. Both primary and secondary data were collected from 46 insurance companies using a 5-point Likert type structured questionnaire. The respondents were the Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) of these firms and in their absence, senior managers were the respondents. Correlation analysis was used to analyze data. The findings revealed that intangible resources had a statistically significant positive moderate correlation with innovation ($r = 0.522$, $p\text{-value} = 0.002$) and process improvements ($r = 0.484$, $p\text{-value} = 0.005$). Tangible resources evidenced a weak positive correlation with innovation that was not statistically significant. Further, results indicated that innovation has a moderate positive correlation with organizational resources that was statistically significant ($r = 0.485$, $p\text{-value} = 0.005$.) This was an indicator that there was a significant relationship between organizational resources and innovation. The results imply that managers of insurance companies should focus on attracting intangible resources if innovation has to improve. Managers will use the findings of this study to identify performance drivers in their organizations. Policy makers should encourage research and development of new products which will enhance insurance penetration and performance of insurance companies in Kenya.

Key Words: Kenya, Resources, Innovation, Insurance Companies

Resources as a Driver of Innovation of Insurance companies in Kenya

By

Dr. Beatrice Ombaka, PhD

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background

Innovation is a key element of corporate competitiveness in the 21st century, and has therefore attracted special attention from strategic management researchers and practitioners. According to OECD (2007), Innovation is at the heart of economic development and as such, it is helpful for developing countries Kenya being among them. Brown and Eisenhardt (1995) proposed that the resources and capabilities owned by a firm determine its capacity to innovate. Thus, firms that have strategic resources will be innovative as compared to their counterparts who do not possess these resources (Brown and Eisenhardt, 1995).

The extant literature proposes that organizational resources influence innovation, and for firms to successfully innovate they need resources (Henderson and Cockburn (1994). According to the Resource Based Theory (RBV), the presence of different organizational resources and capabilities positively affects the outcome of the innovation process. Kostopoulos et al. (2002) propose that organizational resources (tangible and intangible) provide the input that in turn is combined and transformed by capabilities to produce innovative forms of competitive advantage. The availability of financial resources can expand a firm's capacity to support its innovative activities (Lee et al. 2001). Further, Demirkan (2018) proposed that firms that had more financial resources were more likely to take advantage of new opportunities than those with financial constraints and hence invest more in innovation. Therefore, this study sought to establish the effect of organizational resources on innovation of insurance companies in Kenya.

The insurance industry in Kenya plays the financial intermediary role that contributes significantly to the realization of the Kenya Vision 2030. Kenya Vision 2030 aims to achieve an average Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth rate of 10 percent per annum (Kenya Vision 2030 Report, 2007). The insurance industry falls in the financial services sector, which is among the priority sectors that are expected to spur the country's economic growth. This study therefore focuses on insurance companies because their innovativeness will impact on the achievement of the Vision 2030.

1.2 Problem Statement

According to the Association of Kenyan Insurers (AKI) (report (2011), low levels of innovation have over the years led to massive price cutting, a phenomenon that has had a major impact on the growth and profitability of insurance companies in Kenya. Innovation is important to insurance firms because since their products are similar, they therefore need to innovate consistently in order to remain a head of competition.

Lack of innovativeness is evidenced by the fact that insurance penetration in Kenya remains low at 3.3 percent. If these companies have to experience improved performance, they should put more emphasis on innovation. Investment in innovation will help firms to adapt to the dynamic environment in which these firms operate. Studies have been done on the role that resources play in innovation. For instance, Cattani (2005) found that technological performance depended on a firm's stock of relevant resources. His study focused on resources and did not link resources to innovation. Demirkan (2018) investigated

the impact of firm resources on innovation and found that Network-level resources positively impacted innovation. While there is agreement that resources are a driver of innovation, literature still lacks in the role of resources on innovation. This research contributes to Strategic management and innovation literature by establishing the effect of organizational resources on innovation of insurance companies in Kenya.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to establish the effect of resources on innovation of insurance Companies in Kenya.

1.4 Significance of the study

The study serves as a source of information to policy makers not only in the insurance industry but also to the government. The insurance industry is one of the sectors that are envisioned to play a key role in the realization of Kenya's Vision 2030 by contributing to the country's economic growth of 10 percent per annum as spelt in the Kenya Vision 2030. The study will provide a better understanding of how managers can enhance innovation within the insurance industry given the resources a firm owns. This will enable the regulator formulate appropriate policies to enhance competitiveness of the insurance industry. Based on the findings, the study recommends IRA to develop and implement policies that will in the long-run strengthen the industry against past failure and enhance innovativeness as innovation is the driver for growth in the insurance industry.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Theoretical Review

Resource Based Theory (RBT) argues that the competitive advantage of a firm is determined by the key resources it owns. The RBT focuses on internal resources of a firm as a source of Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA). The RBT suggests that unique resources are the source of superior performance (Barney, 1991). Further he proposes that these resources should be Valuable, Rare, non-substitutable and inimitable for the firms to gain a SCA.

The proponents of the Dynamic capability theory are Teece, Pisano, and Shuen in 1997. The dynamic capability theory underscores an organization's capacity to adapt and innovate in response to evolving environments in order to uphold or elevate competitiveness. Dynamic capabilities enable an organization to achieve new and innovative forms of competitive advantage (Leonard-Barton, 1992).

2.2 Resources and Innovation

Marino, (1996) defined resources as assets, knowledge, capabilities, and organizational processes that enable the firm to conceive and implement strategic decisions. He categorized resources in to three categories physical, human and organizational. Penrose (1959) argued that a firm's growth is due to the manner in which its resources are employed. Barney (1991) argued that firms that possessed resources that were valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable would attain a Sustained competitive advantage.

Resources can be classified as tangible or intangible. Bakar and Ahmad (2010) posit that tangible resources include capital, location of buildings, warehouse and other facilities. Conner (2002) argues that tangible resources are a weak source of competitive advantage compared to intangible resources as competitors can easily duplicate them.

Barney, 1991; Hitt et al., (2001) propose that intangible resources are the most important for a firm as they are difficult to imitate. Amit and Schoemaker (1993) proposed

that intangible resources were most likely to be a source SCA as opposed to tangible resources. Intangible resources include employee’s knowledge, experiences and skills, firm’s reputation, brand name, organizational procedures. In-order for firms to prosper, they should have a combination of both tangible and intangible assets. In this study, the specific measures for tangible resources were physical and financial resources while the measures for intangible resources were knowledge and skills, reputation, culture, capabilities and technology. According to Brown and Eisenhardt (1995) and Henderson and Cockburn (1994), the resources and capabilities owned by a firm determine its capacity to innovate.

Scholars argue that in the modern environment characterized by hyper competition, innovation is paramount if firms have to earn a competitive advantage (D’Aveni, 1994). Intense and rapid competitive moves require firms to continuously innovate to create new advantages (Dess and Picken, 2000). According to Schilling (2006), innovation starts from generating new ideas, which later acquire value by being converted into new products, services and processes. As soon as idea is practically implemented it can then be called an innovation. Lundvall (2007) quoting Schumpeter (1934) argues that innovation can be new products, processes, raw materials, forms of organization and markets. Innovation is seen as a culture in which employees are encouraged to challenge and experiment.

Hall et al. (2008) posits that production of new goods reflects innovation activity which has been successful. Product development is one of the mechanisms by which firms create, integrate, recombine, and shed resources. There is empirical evidence that commitment to innovation is a key to success and in the long run can be helpful in earning a competitive advantage for the firm. Cucculelli and Ermini (2012) found that product development promotes growth of firms. In this study, Innovation was measured using Research and Development(R&D) and Process Improvements.

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher 2014

3.0 Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. According to Creswell & Creswell, (2021), research design is the overall strategy or blueprint that a researcher uses to integrate the different components of a study in a coherent and logical manner. It provides a framework for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data (Creswell & Creswell, 2021). The target population was all insurance firms in Kenya and the unit of analysis was the insurance firm. According to the AKI report (2012), there were 46 firms operating in Kenya as at December 2012). Performance of these companies is important as the financial sector in which the insurance companies belong is targeted to help achieve the country's Vision 2030.

Given the population size, all the 46 insurance firms were contacted to participate in the survey. This eliminated accuracy concerns that arise when samples are used. The study collected both primary and secondary data which was largely quantitative using structured questionnaires. The target respondents were senior managers of insurance companies and the study targeted Chief Executive Officers (CEO) or designated director, head of department, general manager or line managers. The senior managers were picked from either marketing department or strategy and risk departments. These respondents were best placed to answer the research questions as they were thought to be knowledgeable and define the direction of the organization. They were thus deemed to be able to provide credible responses. The above is consistent with Campbell (1995) who suggests that key informants should be knowledgeable about the issues being studied and also be willing to communicate the information.

A pretest of the research instrument was conducted on five commercial banks. Pretesting helped the researcher to identify and correct potential issues before the actual data collection began (Connelly, 2018). Feedback received was used to fine-tune the questionnaire before embarking on the actual data collection. According to Cuncic (2022) validity refers to correctness, or whether the results accurately reflect what they are meant to measure. Content validity helped in assessing how well the collected data would align with specific concepts (Kinyanjui, 2020).

Reliability refers to the degree to which a data collection tool consistently produces stable and consistent results over repeated trials (Taherdoost, 2016). Reliability was used to check the internal consistency of the data measuring instrument. Cronbach's coefficient alpha determines the internal consistency or the average correlation of items within the test. The higher the coefficient, the more reliable the measurements scale. Taber, (2018) argued that Cronbach's alpha of 0.7 was accepted and this was taken as the study's threshold.

Table 3.1 Reliability Results

Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Conclusion
Tangible organization resources	7	.703	Reliable
Intangible organization resources	15	.881	Reliable
Innovation	16	.940	Reliable

Source: Field Data 2014

Data were analyzed using inferential statistics and presented in tables.

4.0 Data analysis and Discussion

The objective of the study was to establish the effect of resources on innovation of insurance companies in Kenya. To achieve this objective, correlation analysis was performed to establish the degree of correlation between organizational resources and innovation using Pearson product moment correlation. Innovation was evaluated as R & D and process improvements while resources were evaluated as tangible and intangible. The results are shown in Table 4.1 below.

Table 4.1: Relationship Between Tangible Resources, Intangible Resources, Research and Development and Process Improvements

Variables	Research and Development	Process Improvement
Pearson Correlation	.135	.277
Tangible resources	.460	.125
	Sig. (2-tailed)	
Pearson Correlation	.522**	.484**
Intangible resources		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Data (2014)

Table 4.1 presents results of the correlation between tangible and intangible resources and R & D and process improvements. A moderate and positive relationship was observed between intangible resources and R & D ($r = 0.522$, p -value = 0.002). There was also a moderate and positive relationship between intangible resources and process improvements ($r = 0.484$, p -value = 0.005). This means that intangible resources are significantly related to R & D and process improvements. The results imply that managers of insurance companies should focus on attracting intangible resources if innovation has to improve.

The results indicate that intangible resources significantly influence both R & D and process improvements in tandem with previous research findings and the RBT which propose that intangible resources are the primary predictors of innovation (Song & Parry, 1997). However, a weak positive statistically not significant relationship was observed between tangible resources and both R & D and process improvements. This finding contradicts findings from previous empirical studies that have found a relationship between tangible resources and innovation (Lee et al., 2001).

The study further sought to establish the relationship between resources and innovation by using the composite index for resources and the composite index for innovation. Table 4.2 presents correlation results between innovation and organizational resources.

Table 4.2: Relationship Between Resources and Innovation

Variables	Innovation	Organization Resources
Pearson Correlation	1	.485**
Innovation		.005
		Sig. (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source Field Data (2014)

The results in Table 4.2 indicate that innovation has a moderate positive correlation with organizational resources that was statistically significant ($r = 0.485$, p -value = 0.005.) This was an indicator that there is a significant relationship between organizational resources and innovation. The results imply that for innovation to take place, firms should possess adequate resources consistent with the RBT which states that the presence of different organizational resources and capabilities positively affect the outcome of the innovation process (Kostopolous et al., 2002).

The findings support previous studies that found a positive relationship between intangible resources and innovation. Bakar and Ahmad (2010) studying small firms in Malaysia found that intangible resources were the main drivers of innovation. This is consistent with the RBV that states that intangible resources are the main drivers of innovation and hence performance (Barney, 1991).

Empirical and theoretical literature proposes that certain resources are important for innovation to take place. Lee et al. (2001) proposed that firms that had adequate financial resources had the capacity to expand their innovative activities. Conversely, Teece and Pisano (1994) argued that lack of financial resources inhibits the firm's ability to innovate. Results of this study did not support this proposition as there was no correlation between tangible resources and R & D and process improvements.

The results revealed that intangible resources have a strong positive correlation with both R&D and process improvement indicating that insurance companies should focus on acquiring intangible resources as they will enhance innovation. The results indicate that intangible resources influence innovation while tangible resources do not influence innovation. The results of this study support previous empirical and theoretical studies. Song & Parry (1997) proposed that technical resources like Information Technology (IT) systems had a significant influence on firm performance while Barney (1991), proposed that intangible resources are more important than tangible resources since they were hard to imitate.

Song & Parry (1997) argue that organizations with qualified human personnel will be more likely to spur the firm to be more innovative. The results of this study suggest that insurance companies should pay more attention to intangible resources if they are to be innovative. As suggested through theoretical literature, intangible resources such as knowledge that is embedded in employees will lead to innovative ideas that are the beginning of the innovative process.

Conclusion

The study examined the relationship between organizational resources and innovation of insurance companies in Kenya. Results suggested a positive moderate correlation between intangible resources and innovation. There was a weak correlation between tangible resources and innovation that was not statistically significant. These results are important to practice as managers should invest more in intangible resources as they are important drivers of innovation. The findings are important for managers of insurance companies. If these firms have to be innovative, they need resources as studies have established that lack of resources can influence a firm's capacity to innovate. These findings thus support previous studies that have found that firms need to have different kinds of resources to support innovative activities.

Recommendation

Policy makers should encourage research and development of new products which will enhance insurance penetration and performance of insurance companies in Kenya. Insurance companies should pay more attention to intangible resources if they are to be innovative. Managers of these firms to invest more in intangible resources because they are drivers of innovation.

Reference

- Amit, R., & Schoemaker, P. (1993). Strategic assets and organizational rent. *Strategic Management Journal*, 14 (1), 33-46.
- Association of Kenya Insurers (2011). *Insurance industry annual report*, 1 (33), 1-64.
- Bakar, L. J. A., & Ahmad, H. (2010). Assessing the relationship between firm resources and product innovation performance: A resource based view. *Business Process Management Journal*, 16 (3), 420-435.
- Barney, J. B. (1999). How a firm's capabilities affect boundary decisions. *Sloan Management Review*, 40, 137-145.
- Brown, S. L., & Eisenhardt, K. M. (1995). Product development: Past research, present findings, and future directions: *The Academy of Management Review*, 20 (2), 343-378.
- Cattani, G. (2005). Preadaptation, firm heterogeneity, and technological performance: A study on the evolution of fiber optics, 1970–1995. *Organization Science*, 16, 563–580.
- Campbell, J. Y. (1995). Some lessons from the yield curve. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 9, 129-152.
- Connelly, L. M. (2018). Pilot studies. *MedSurg Nursing*, 17(6), 411-412.
<https://www.medsurnursing.net/cgi-bin/WebObjects/MSNJournal.woa>
- Conner, T. (2002). The resource-based view of strategy and its value to practicing managers. *Strategic Change*, 11, 307-316.
- Conner, K. R. (1991). A historical comparison of resource-based theory and five schools of thought within industrial organization economics: Do we have a new theory of the firm? *Journal of Management*, 17, 121-154.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, D. J. (2021). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Cucculelli, M., & Ermini, B. (2012). New product introduction and product tenure: What effects on firm growth? *Research Policy*, 41, 808– 821.
- Cuncic, A. (2022). How to develop and practice self-regulation?
<https://www.verywellmind.com/how-you-can-practice-self-regulation-4163536>
- D’Aveni, R. (1994). *Hyper-competition: Managing the dynamics of strategic maneuvering*. New York: The Free Press.
- Dess, G. G., & Picken, J. C. (2000). Changing roles: Leadership in the 21st century. *Organizational Dynamics*, 28, 18–34.
- Hitt, M. A., Bierman, L., Shimizu, K., & Kochhar, R. (2001). Direct and moderating effects of human capital on strategy and performance in professional services firms: A resource-based perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44, 13-28
- Irem Demirkan, (2018) "The impact of firm resources on innovation", *European Journal of Innovation Management*, Vol. 21 Issue: 4, pp.672-694, <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-12-2017-0196>
Permanent link to this document:<https://doi.org/10.1108/EJIM-12-2017-019>
- Kinyanjui, S. (2020). Strategic Planning and Resource Allocation in Kenyan Universities. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9(2), 120-135.
- Kostopoulos, K. C., Spanos Y. E., & Prastacos, G. P. (2002). The resource – based view of the firm and innovation: Identification of critical linkages. *The 2nd European Academy of Management Conference*, Stockholm.

- Lee, C., Lee, K., & Pennings, J. M., (2001). Internal capabilities, external networks, and performance: A study on technology-based ventures. *Strategic Management Journal*, 22, 615-640.
- Leonard-Barton, D. (1992). Core capabilities and core rigidities: A paradox in managing new product development. *Strategic Management Journal*, 13 (Special Issue), 111-125
- Lundvall, B. (2007). National innovation systems: Analytical concept and development tool. *Industry and innovation*, 14 (1), 95-119.
- Marino, K. E. (1996). Developing consensus on firm competencies and capabilities. *Academy of Management Executive*, 10 (3), 40-51.
- OECD (2007). *Innovation and growth: Rationale for an innovation strategy*.
- Schilling, M. (2006). *Strategic management of technological innovation*. (2nd ed.). New-York: McGraw-Hill.
- Schumpeter, J. (1934). *The theory of economic development: An inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest and business cycle*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Song, X. M., & Parry, M. E. (1997). The determinants of Japanese new product successes. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 34 (1), 64–76.
- Taherdoost, H. (2016). Validity and reliability of the research instrument; How to test the validation of a questionnaire/survey in a research. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management*, 5(3), 28-36.
DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.3205040
- Teece, D. J., Pisano, G., & Shuen, A. (1997). Dynamic capabilities and strategic management. *Strategic Management Journal*, 18 (8), 509-533.